

THE ROLE OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TEXTILE AND GARMENT INDUSTRY IN UZBEKISTAN IN INCREASING NATIONAL COMPETITIVENESS

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***Abstract.** In this article, the production of textile products - preparation and spinning of textile fiber, as well as the production of textile yarns and finished textile products, decoration of textile products and clothes, production of finished textile products other than clothes, their analysis, The formation of cotton-textile clusters and cooperation between large textile companies with Uzbekistan are also being considered.*

***Keywords:** textile products, business, market, competition, cluster, investment, export.*

Introduction. The Republic of Uzbekistan, striving to find its place in the world community, is implementing a strategy of rapid development in the political and economic spheres. In particular, the establishment of goals such as forming a competitive advantage in the international market, increasing and implementing export potential, and promoting the name of our country is associated with the implementation of deep reforms in all sectors of the real economy.

Uzbekistan differs significantly from other countries in its natural and geographical location and historical and social characteristics, in particular:

-Today, our country is one of only two countries in the world that needs to cross two or more borders to reach the sea. Our geographical location creates logistical problems in exporting, increases the cost of products, and reduces their competitiveness. In this situation, the only alternative is a strategy of deep processing of raw materials, an emphasis on innovative products, and the introduction of scientific and technological achievements into production;

-Uzbekistan is historically one of the countries with great experience and glory in the production of agricultural products. Our country is among the top five in the production of cotton fiber. Uzbekistan ranks first in Central Asia in the export of silk, cotton, leather, fruits and vegetables. This situation has a significant impact on the structure of the manufacturing industry of our economy. The availability of a raw material base has become the basis for the development of light industry enterprises and the creation of national brands in this area.

-The volume and qualitative composition of labor resources in the Republic of Uzbekistan are based on extensive experience and skills in processing raw materials. Our country has created historical social traditions in the production and processing of natural raw materials, and the national values of our people and the opportunities for global social specialization are adapted to the light industry. The provision of labor resources serves as an important factor in the development of industries with high demand for labor.

Analysis of literature on the topic. In increasing national competitiveness The analysis of the available literature shows the need to improve modern market principles, brand promotion methods and a flexible approach to consumer requirements. In his textbook on market strategies,

the expert RGIbragimov states the following: “Marketing strategy is understood as the use of a model of the principles of the enterprise's behavior in the market, established for a certain period of time. With its help, the enterprise seeks to ensure its success.” Many economists have been involved in the development and implementation of marketing strategies. Among them are such famous scientists as F. Kotler, David Aaker, Clayton Christensen, Seth Godin, Kevin Keller, Byron Sharp, and Jay Bayer.

While the research conducted in the field of marketing in our country for many years is based on national characteristics, it is also necessary to recognize the scientists who have made a significant contribution to the development of marketing theory. These include R.Ibragimov, YO.Abdullaev, A.Saliev, M.Sharifkhodjaev, D.Rakhimova, Sh.Ergashkhodjaeva, Sh.Musayeva and others..

Research methodology. The study used a systematic approach, marketing analysis, benchmarking, and digital metrics. Mass surveillance methods were used to collect and analyze data from social media platforms.

Analysis and results. The textile and garment industry is recognized as one of the most important areas of light industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The place of these industrial enterprises can be seen in the following analytical table (Table 1.1). This table shows the dynamics of the development of our country's industry, manufacturing industry, and in particular, the textile and clothing manufacturing industry in 2017-2024.

Table 1.1.

Development of textile and clothing production in Uzbekistan in 2017-2024

Classifier	unit of measurement	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Industrial output, total	trillion soums	148.8	235.3	322.5	368.7	456.1	553.3	659.8	885.80
Of this, Manufacturing industry	trillion soums	120.7	189.6	254.9	305.9	378.2	460.5	556.4	753.60
Production of textile products	trillion soums	16.76	24.83	29.94	36.72	52.37	62.85	71.51	89.45
Clothing production	trillion soums	6.11	7.73	9.17	10.4	13.59	17.26	23.09	33.76
The share of textile production in the manufacturing industry	%	13.89	13.1	11.75	12.0	13.85	13.65	12.85	11.87
The share of clothing production in the manufacturing industry	%	5.06	4.08	3.6	3.40	3.59	3.75	4.15	4.48
The share of textile and clothing	%	18.95	17.17	15.35	15.4	17.44	17.4	17	16.35

production in the manufacturing industry									
physical volume index compared to the corresponding period of the previous year									
Production of textile products	%	100. 5	107. 4	105.3	117. 4	119. 5	109. 9	106. 4	111.1
Clothing production	%	110. 5	103. 3	108.7	107. 2	118. 7	105. 8	112. 7	109.4

First of all, we believe that it is necessary to pay attention to the sharp increase in the volume of industrial products in our country. During the observed period, this sector has shown an almost six-fold increase (from 148.8 trillion soums to 885.8 trillion soums). The growth rate of the manufacturing industry within it is somewhat higher, that is, by 6.24 times, which indicates that the processing of raw materials is much higher than the extraction of raw materials. If we analyze the development of the textile and sewing and knitwear industry, which is the object of our study, we will see that over the past period, the production of textile products has increased from 16.76 trillion soums to 89.45 trillion soums (by 5.34 times), and the production of clothing from 6.11 trillion soums to 33.76 trillion soums (by 5.33 times).

The share of textile and sewing-knitting industry in the manufacturing industry was 18.95 percent in 2017, and it was equal to 16.35 percent in 2024, which is a decrease of 2.6 percent. Therefore, even today, every sixth product created in the manufacturing industry belongs to the product of the textile and sewing-knitting industry. These data show the importance of this sector in the economic potential of our country.

Production of textile products - includes preparation and spinning of textile fiber, as well as production of textile yarns and ready-made textile products, decoration of textile products and clothes, production of ready-made textile products other than clothes.

Clothing production includes the production of sewn products from all materials (ready-made or made to order), all types of clothing (for example, outerwear, underwear for men, women and children, work, office, casual or sportswear, etc.) and accessories. In January-December 2023, the share of textile production in the manufacturing industry structure was 12.9%, the physical volume index increased by 6.4% compared to the corresponding period of the previous year, and the production volume amounted to 71,121.1 billion soums. In January-December 2023, the share of clothing production in the manufacturing industry structure was 4.1%, the physical volume index increased by 109.9% compared to the corresponding period of the previous year, and the production volume amounted to 22,478.3 billion soums.

In January-December 2024, the share of textile production in the manufacturing industry was 11.9%, the physical volume index increased by 11.1% compared to the corresponding period of the previous year, and the production volume corresponds to 89,451.2 billion soums. If we analyze the activity of the textile industry in 2024, the production of textile products in our country was equal to 89.5 trillion soums, and the production of clothes amounted to 33.8 trillion soums

(123.3 trillion soums in total). In 2023, textile and clothing production amounted to 94.6 trillion soums. This shows that the share of manufacturing industry reached 16.4%. In January-December 2024, the share of clothing production in the manufacturing industry was 4.5%, the physical volume index increased by 9.4% compared to the corresponding period of the previous year, and the production volume amounted to 33,764.2 billion soums. The following diagrams show the graphs of changes in the production volume and physical volume of textile and clothing products in 2027-2024 (Figures 1 and 2).

Figure 1. Changes in textile and clothing production in Uzbekistan in 2017-2024, billion soums.

Figure 2. Index of physical volume of textile and clothing production in 2017-2024, %.

Behind the above figures lie the large-scale reforms being carried out in the republic and the hard work of industry specialists. The main reason for this is the strong competition in the world textile market and the objective need for state support for the industry to enter it and compete on an

equal footing. Over the past decade, many institutional and economic mechanisms have been developed to increase the export potential of national textile and knitting enterprises, and the achievements achieved today are largely due to their implementation.

First of all, we would like to draw attention to the creation of a regulatory and legal framework aimed at increasing the competitiveness of the textile and garment industry. The President of our country pays great attention to the development of the textile industry, and in the past year several decrees and resolutions have been issued to further develop this sector.

The starting point for a radical reform of the textile industry in New Uzbekistan can be considered the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 5285, adopted on December 14, 2017. The goals set out in this decree were reflected in the Development Strategy for 2017-2021, and later in the Development Strategy for New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026.

During 2017-2022, the volume of textile exports from Uzbekistan increased almost fourfold. In 2017, our country supplied textile products worth \$880 million to 49 countries, while in 2021 the number of countries to which Uzbek products came reached 67, and the volume reached \$3 billion. By the end of this year, this figure is expected to increase to \$3 billion. \$3.5 billion. In 2027, Uzbekistan intends to supply textile products worth \$10 billion to more than 90 countries around the world¹.

Today, the following can be included among the main achievements of the textile and sewing-knitting industry of our country:

Recognition of Uzbekistan as an equal partner in the international market. Major reforms implemented by our President, the abolition of forced and child labor in the production of cotton raw materials, have allowed the international community to enter the market for Uzbek cotton and its products. The formation of cotton-textile clusters has also led to cooperation between large textile companies with Uzbekistan. As a result, Uzbekistan received GSP+ preferences from the European Union, i.e., more than 6,000 goods were exempted from export taxes when entering the European market. The fact that only eight countries in the world have such privileges indicates high confidence in Uzbekistan. Textile products manufactured in Uzbekistan are sold in stores of such famous brands as Hugo Boss, Diesel, Tendam, Inditex, El Corte, Engelberg Straus, The North Face, Collins, S.Oliver, LC Waikiki, De Facto, Pierre Cardin, Falke.

Becoming the center of the textile industry in Central Asia and the CIS countries. The "Uzbek model" of textile industry development is being widely implemented in all neighboring countries and is bearing fruit. Uzbek enterprises have established mutually beneficial cooperation with partners from Central Asia, Georgia, Armenia, and Azerbaijan. More than half of the textile products produced in the republic are exported to the CIS countries. In recent years, such cooperation has been established with countries such as China, South Korea, and Pakistan.

- leadership in sustainable development and compliance with international standards. This sector of the manufacturing industry is traditionally one of the most energy-intensive industries. The measures taken gradually in our country have created an economic basis for the creation of innovative ideas for energy saving and the introduction of technologies that meet international environmental standards. As a result of the efforts made in recent years, the consumption of

¹<https://yuz.uz/ru/news/razvitie-tekstilnoy-i-shvey-no-trikotajnoy-promshlennosti-uzbekistana-v-2017-2022-godax-infografika>

electricity and natural gas per unit of output has decreased by 23.5% compared to 2017, and this process continues.

The President's policy aimed at ensuring that textile products take their place in the international market in terms of quality is also noteworthy. "For example, in the textile industry, about 7 thousand entrepreneurs produce more than 500 types of products. Some of them supply clothing to prestigious brands. However, although many work for quality, they cannot demonstrate it. So far, only 244 of our enterprises have international certificates. Most of them are located in Tashkent and the valley regions, and in other regions they can be counted on the fingers."

Along with the benefits and financial support for textile and garment enterprises, the investment policy of our country is also of great importance. In particular, the importance of the manufacturing industry in targeting foreign investments in our country has been unparalleled.

As a result of the above actions, favorable business conditions are being created for national textile enterprises. At the same time, there is a problem of strengthening the marketing system aimed at ensuring international competitiveness in textile and garment enterprises, which indicates the need to deepen scientific research in this area.

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